

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Abdukhalikova I.

1st year master's student of Angren University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14563155>

Abstract. *School education is structured in such a way that verbal-logical thinking receives preferential development. If at first much attention is paid to working with visual examples, then starting from the third grade the volume of such activities is sharply reduced. The figurative principle loses its necessity in educational activity. Children master the techniques of mental activity, acquire the ability to act in the mind and analyze the process of their own reasoning.*

The development of the thinking activity of a child of primary school age has its own characteristics and is determined by a natural change of stages, in which each previous one prepares the subsequent ones. With the emergence of new forms of thinking, the old forms do not disappear, they are preserved and developed.

Keywords: *development, pedagogy, formation, thinking activity, primary school age, features, regular, new forms of thinking, develop.*

Mathematics and its inherent style of thinking are part of the culture and education of modern man. Today, teaching mathematics at school consists not only in the assimilation of factual knowledge by students, but also in mastering mathematical methods. Universal mathematical methods of cognition contribute to a holistic perception of the world, allow us to build models of individual processes and phenomena, and are also the basis for the formation of universal educational activities. Possession of such qualities of mathematical style of thinking as criticality, evidence, abstractness, laconism are required for a person of any sphere of activity. It is no coincidence that the Standard of primary general education in the section on mathematics puts the task of developing logical thinking and spatial imagination of students to the forefront.

The main goal of studying mathematics is to develop a comprehensively developed and proactive personality, possessing a system of mathematical knowledge and skills, cultural, ideological, moral and ethical principles, and norms of behavior that are formed in the process of educational activities and prepare the student for active work in modern society[2].

Summarizing the main provisions of the concept of mathematical education [3], the primary school mathematics course helps to solve the following problems: • ensure a strong and conscious assimilation of the system of mathematical knowledge and skills necessary for further education; • form intellectual development, develop logic and the way of thinking necessary for a full life in society; • create and develop a desire to learn; • promote the development of a sustainable interest in mathematics; • identify and develop mathematical and creative abilities. Work on the development of logical thinking in primary school is of particular importance [22]. The beginning of education implies the development of thinking as the center of the child's mental development and as a determining factor in the system of other mental functions, which, under the influence of thinking, acquire an arbitrary character. The thinking of younger schoolchildren is at a turning point in its development. [21] During this period, the transition from visual-figurative thinking to verbal-logical thinking occurs, which introduces a dual character into the student's mental activity: concrete thinking, based on reality and direct observations, is already subject to

logical principles, but abstract, formal-logical reasoning is not yet available to children. Thinking techniques are not formed automatically. The main task of the teacher: to work actively and skillfully in this direction, organizing the learning process so that by enriching children with knowledge, to form thinking techniques, to promote the development of cognitive abilities of schoolchildren. In the National Curriculum, the State Educational Standard of Primary General Education sets the main task for primary education - the development of independence and logic of thinking, which would allow students to provide evidence, build conclusions, statements that are logically connected with each other, draw conclusions, justifying their judgments, and, ultimately, independently acquire knowledge [8].

Logical techniques and operations are the main components of logical thinking, which begins to develop intensively precisely at primary school age. Teaching practice shows that the goal of each lesson in almost every subject is to develop students' thinking. Previously it was believed that logical thinking develops by itself in mathematics lessons, without any special work. Only a few researchers, such as V.A. Gusev, M.I. Zaikin, A.Z. Zak, V.A. Kolosova, Yu.M. Kolyagin, L.M. Likhtarnikov, E.E. Ostanina, L.G. Peterson, D. Poyga, G.I. Sarancev, Ch. Phillips, L.M. Friedman, and others, paid special attention to the role of mathematics in the process of developing logical thinking.

The process of thinking has interested man since ancient times. Even ancient philosophers reflected on its role in human life. Thus, the Greek philosopher Socrates considered thinking as a way of knowing the world and oneself, and in the process of such knowledge a person improves himself [18]. Aristotle linked conscious thinking with sensations as the starting point of knowledge. The thought process, in his opinion, consists of generalizing the acquired knowledge, and goes from the concrete to the abstract. In the 17th century, René Descartes, a famous French philosopher and mathematician [19], also emphasized the importance of thinking and being in human life: "I think – therefore I exist". The 17th century Dutch rationalist philosopher Benedict Spinoza, in his work "A Treatise on the Improvement of Reason and on the Way to the True Knowledge of Things" [19], speaks of four types of knowledge. He distinguished knowledge of individual things, which is given to the mind by the senses, knowledge by recollection, knowledge by reasoning, based on knowledge of general concepts and general properties of things. The 18th century German thinker Immanuel Kant laid the foundation for the typology of thinking, dividing it into formal thinking and dialectical thinking, concrete and abstract, as well as practical and dialectical [18]. The Philosophical Dictionary [15] defines thinking as a human cognitive activity, the result of which is a thought, the formation of a concept, the awareness of meaning and an idea. Thinking is contrasted with "lower" ways of mastering the world in the form of sensation or perception, which are also characteristic of animals. Psychologists began studying thinking in the 17th century; the ability to think was considered innate at that time, and thinking itself was identified with logic. In the 20th century, when experimentally studying the process of thinking, scientists were divided into two groups: the first group included supporters of the assertion that human intellectual abilities are a natural gift and cannot be developed; the second group believed that these abilities can be formed and developed during life. In associative empirical psychology, there was an opinion that thinking is a process of randomly sorting through different associations. Thinking is a set of mental processes that underlie cognition; thinking specifically includes the active side of cognition: attention, perception, the process of associations, the formation of concepts and judgments [16]. In a narrower logical sense, thinking includes only the formation of

judgments and conclusions through the analysis and synthesis of concepts. Thinking is a process of cognitive activity of an individual, characterized by a generalized and mediated reflection in the consciousness of a person of connections and relationships between objects and phenomena of reality.

Thinking is a function of the human brain, a special form where its reflex, analytical-synthetic activity is manifested, which has support in the second signal system. The process of thinking is accomplished with the help of mental operations: comparison, analysis, synthesis, abstraction, generalization and concretization, allowing to reveal all the important connections and relationships between objects, phenomena and facts [4]. Psychologists have identified the characteristics of thinking as a mental process [6]: Firstly, thinking is characterized by its indirect nature. If a person fails to know something directly, immediately, then he can know it indirectly, mediately: some properties are known through others, the unknown is known through the known [14]. Secondly, thinking is characterized by its generality. Generalization as knowledge of the general and essential in objects of reality occurs because all the properties of these objects are related to each other. The general exists and manifests itself only in something separate, concrete. People express generalizations with the help of speech, language. The function of thinking is to expand the boundaries of knowledge by going beyond the limits of sensory perception. With the help of thinking, using inferences, it is possible to reveal what is not obtained directly through perception. Generalizations that a person makes in the process of thinking are fixed in concepts that reflect the totality of the essential properties of an object. Thirdly, thinking is always connected with the solution of a particular problem that has arisen in the process of cognition or in practical activity. The process of thinking is most clearly manifested only when a problem situation arises that needs to be solved: a question appears, the answer to which is the goal of thinking. Moreover, the answer to this question is not found immediately, but with the help of certain mental operations, during which the modification and transformation of the available information occurs. Fourthly, thinking is closely connected with speech, this is another extremely important feature[5].

Thoughts are always clothed in speech form, even in cases where speech does not have a sound form, for example in the case of deaf-mute people. We always think in words, we cannot think without pronouncing words. The task of thinking is to reveal the relationships between objects, to identify connections and to separate them from random coincidences. Thinking uses concepts and operates with them and takes on the functions of generalization and planning. Thinking is a complex and multifaceted mental activity, therefore its types are distinguished on various grounds: by form, by the nature of the tasks being solved, by the degree of development, by the degree of novelty and originality. Theoretical imaginative thinking is associated with the use of images by a person in the process of thinking, their transformation and manipulation. These images can be extracted directly from long-term memory or created by a person's imagination. Thanks to this type of thinking, it is possible to most fully recreate many different factual characteristics of an object. In an image, it is possible to record a simultaneous vision of an object from different points of view [3].

An important feature of figurative thinking is the establishment of unusual, “incredible” combinations of objects and their properties. The main task of figurative thinking is the creation of images and their transformation in accordance with the task at hand. In this case, existing images are transformed and new images are created in accordance with new data. Figurative thinking uses the operations of recognition, selection, formation, transformation and generalization of the

content of the reflection of the figurative form. Both theoretical conceptual and theoretical figurative thinking complement each other, allowing a person to perceive the surrounding reality most fully. Practical types of thinking are directly related to the perception of the surrounding reality and cannot be accomplished without relying on it. Visual-figurative practical thinking operates with images presented in operational and short-term memory; the image is not transformed. A person finds a solution to a problem by observing objects, but without touching them. Visual-effective practical thinking is directly related to transformative activity carried out with real objects. In the process of such thinking, the process of solving a problem is carried out with the help of real, physical transformations of the situation, objects, testing of properties. There is an opinion that theoretical thinking is more perfect than practical, and conceptual thinking represents a higher level of development than figurative thinking, that is, types of thinking are perceived as levels of its development. However, we are convinced that all types of thinking are closely related to each other, with the emergence of new forms of thinking, old forms do not disappear, they are preserved and developed[4].

For the formation of full-fledged theoretical thinking, a necessary condition is the formation and development of all forms of thinking, starting with visual-effective. Our conviction is based on the conclusions of Yu. R. Valkman: in the process of thinking, both “figurative” and “conceptual” logic are simultaneously present, and these are not two independent logics, but a single logic of the flow of the thought process [7]. Many people have both practical (visual-effective and visual-figurative) and theoretical (conceptual and figurative) thinking developed to the same extent. Depending on the nature of the tasks facing a person, one type of thinking or another becomes dominant. To summarize the above, thinking is an indirect and generalized process of cognition (reflection) of the surrounding world. The task of thinking is to reveal the relationships between objects, identify connections and separate them from random coincidences.

Thinking uses concepts and operates with them and assumes the functions of generalization and planning. According to the nature of the tasks to be solved, the following types of thinking are distinguished: theoretical and practical. Theoretical thinking includes conceptual and figurative thinking, and practical thinking includes visual-effective and visual-figurative thinking. Children of the same age have quite different levels of thinking development. Consequently, teachers and psychologists should take a differentiated approach to the process of thinking development in primary school children[5].

Logical thinking presupposes the child's ability to perform basic logical operations: generalization, analysis, comparison, classification. The most important thinking operations in the learning process are analysis and synthesis [17]. Analysis involves identifying the elements of a given object, its attributes and properties. At the first stage, junior schoolchildren identify only individual parts and properties of an object, i.e. they can only perform a partial analysis. Then, the ability to analyze all the properties of an object is formed, but without establishing the relationships between them. And only after this, a junior schoolchild is able to analyze all the properties and attributes of an object and establish the relationships between them. Synthesis is the combination of various elements and aspects of an object into a single whole. In the thinking activity of students, analysis and synthesis complement each other, since analysis is carried out through synthesis, and synthesis through analysis [20]. Abstraction is the selection of any side or aspect of a phenomenon for the purpose of their separate study [20].

One of the features of abstraction in primary school students is that they sometimes take external, bright, frequently perceived features for essential features. Another feature is that children more easily abstract the properties of objects and phenomena than the connections and relationships that exist between them. Knowing these features, the teacher should draw the students' attention to hidden but essential features, their connections and relationships. For example, when creating a subject model of a task, we abstract from the shape, color of the objects used, the main thing is their number. Comparison, as a mental operation in younger students, also has its own characteristics. This is expressed in the substitution of comparison by the juxtaposition of objects [6] - first they talk about one object, and then about another.

At this age, children find it difficult to compare objects with which they cannot directly act. Therefore, teaching comparison should be carried out in stages, in close connection with the study of specific material. At first, objects or drawings depicting objects that are familiar to them can be used as objects, in which they can identify certain features based on existing ideas. At the first stage, they are taught to identify the features or properties of one object, at the second stage - to identify similarities and differences between the features of two objects, at the third - to establish similarities between the features of three, four or more objects. Generalization is the identification of the main features of objects or phenomena and their properties. The peculiarities of generalization of primary school students consist in the allocation of the most noticeable external features of objects. Generalization proceeds in close unity with concretization.

The assimilation of concepts, laws, rules occurs on the basis of consideration of individual objects, facts, signs, schemes and performance of specific actions with them. The assimilated concepts, laws, rules are applied to the solution of particular specific problems. Thus, in the process of teaching mathematics, generalization is used in the formulation of mathematical rules, identification of regularities. Concretization is a mental transition from the more general to the less general, from the general to the individual. The process of concretization is the opposite of the processes of abstraction and generalization.

Teaching concretization in the educational process is understood in the sense that the teacher must teach students to confirm the general provisions of mathematics with specific examples. For example, the sum does not change from the rearrangement of the terms: $2 + 3$ equal to $3 + 2$, since both of these sums are equal to 5. As for the process of developing the thinking of primary school students, psychologists distinguish two main stages here. At the first stage (grades 1–2), their thinking is practically no different from that of preschoolers: the analysis of educational material occurs primarily in a visual-active and visual-figurative manner. Students reason about objects and phenomena based on their external individual features, superficially, one-sidedly.

Their inferences are based on visual premises given in perception, and conclusions are made without relying on logical arguments, but by directly correlating judgments with perceived information. Concepts and generalizations at this age are strongly associated with the external characteristics of objects and are based on those properties that lie on the surface [13]. By the third grade, thinking moves to a qualitatively new, second stage, requiring the teacher to demonstrate in detail the connections that exist between individual elements of the material being studied. During this period, children learn the generic relationships between individual features of concepts, they develop an analytical-synthetic type of activity, and master the action of modeling. This determines the beginning of the formation of verbal-logical thinking.

Thus, the development of a child's thinking activity has its own characteristics and is determined by a natural change of stages, in which each previous one prepares the following ones. With the emergence of new forms of thinking, the old forms do not disappear, they are preserved and developed. Younger schoolchildren become able to solve more complex cognitive tasks. They develop the ability to reason, justify their judgments, compare, generalize, and concretize. The transition from visual-figurative to verbal-logical thinking occurs.

The main feature of L.V. Zankov's methodology is the property of variability, which implies a change in the teacher's style of work depending on the specific conditions (opportunities) of the class: this may concern the logic of the presentation of the material, and manifest itself in the attitude towards the students. The teacher's tasks and questions are formed in such a way that they contribute to the formulation of different points of view, different assessments, attitudes to the studied material, and do not require an unambiguous answer and action. L.V. Zankov believes that the lesson should be structured differently from the traditional idea, when most of the time was filled with the teacher's speech[13].

Of course, this requires great skill from the teacher: while maintaining their leading role, it is necessary to ensure the freedom of self-realization of the student, to create such conditions so that from the first steps of being in the lesson the child is not afraid to express his thoughts, his observations. For this, it is important to learn to ask children questions that require variant, and not unambiguous answers.

Thus, speaking about the development of logical thinking of children according to L.V. Zankov, we will highlight the following:

- during the study of the material there should be a clash of knowledge and its contradictions, and the students in most cases resolve the conflict themselves;
- the use of variability in learning, where the child is not afraid to give the wrong answer, since there are several points of view on the problem from different sides.

Developmental learning, aimed at the mental development of the child, creates conditions for personal development and growth. In general, developmental learning, as a system, provides education with the means to achieve those goals that were previously only mentioned in the works of various authors, but not all teachers could implement them in the classroom.

REFERENCES

1. Bantova M.A. Methods of Teaching Mathematics in Primary Schools: Textbook / M.A. Bantova, M.A. Beltyukov - 3rd ed., translated by - M.: Education, 1984. - 335 p.
2. Dzhumaev M.I. Competence- based approach to teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements in the national curriculum of Uzbekistan Science and innovation. International Scientific Journal Volume 3 Issue 2 February 2024 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694172>
3. Djumaev, M.I. Algorithm - methodological training of future primary school teachers in teaching primary science / M.I. Djumaev, M.M. Djumaeva // Bulletin of Dulaty University. - 2024. - No. 2. - P. 75-81 MRNTI 14.35.09 <https://doi.org/10.55956/MQKC8014>
4. Djumaev M.I. Competence-based approach in teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements of the national curriculum of Uzbekistan. Shymkent "KhDU" baspasy ISBN 9965-544-22-0 2024 - 306-311
5. Djumaev M.I. Development of mathematical competence of future primary school teachers in the educational process. Proceedings of the III International Scientific and Practical

- Conference "Modern Problems of Teaching Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in Secondary and Higher Schools" (May 16, 2024). Under the general editorship of M. Nugmonov. - Dushanbe: Printing House of TSPU named after S. Aini, 2024. - Pp. 100-106
6. Baillef, J. K. Logical problems [Text] / J. K. Baillef; trans. from French by Yu. N. Sudareva. - M.: Mir, 1983. - 172 p.
 7. Belokurova, E. E. Teaching the solution of combinatorial problems using tables and graphs [Text] // Primary school. - 1995. - No. 1. - P. 21-24. 6. Belyaeva, V. N. Development of logical thinking of schoolchildren in the study of morphology in the 4th grade [Text]: taking into account the peculiarities of the local dialect / V. N. Belyaeva. - Sverdlovsk, [b. i.], 1980. - 48 p
 8. Goncharova, O. S. Development of logical thinking in mathematics lessons in elementary grades [Electronic resource] // Young scientist. – 2012. – No. 10. – P. 329-331. — URL <https://moluch.ru/archive/45/5505/> (date of access: 30.12.2018).
 9. Dzhumaev M.I. Competence- based approach to teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements in the national curriculum of Uzbekistan Science and innovation. International Scientific Journal Volume 3 Issue 2 February 2024 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10694172>
 10. Djumaev, M.I. Algorithm - methodological training of future primary school teachers in teaching primary science / M.I. Djumaev, M.M. Djumaeva // Bulletin of Dulaty University. - 2024. - No. 2. - P. 75-81 MRNTI 14.35.09 <https://doi.org/10.55956/MQKC8014>
 11. Djumaev M.I. Competence-based approach in teaching mathematics to primary school students according to the requirements of the national curriculum of Uzbekistan. Shymkent "KhDU" baspasy ISBN 9965-544-22-0 2024 - 306-311
 12. Djumaev M.I. Development of mathematical competence of future primary school teachers in the educational process. Proceedings of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Modern Problems of Teaching Mathematics, Computer Science and Physics in Secondary and Higher Schools" (May 16, 2024). Under the general editorship of M. Nugmonov. - Dushanbe: Printing House of TSPU named after S. Aini, 2024. - Pp. 100-106
 13. Zankov, L. V. Selected pedagogical works [Text] / L. V. Zankov; introduction by Sh. A. Amonashvili. - M.: Novaya shk., 1996. - 432 p.
 14. Komensky, Ya. A. Selected pedagogical works [Text] / Ya. A. Komensky. : in 2 volumes. - M.: Pedagogy, 1982. - Vol. 1 - 656 p.
 15. Kopytov, N. A. Tasks for the development of logic: an introduction to the language of mathematics [Text]: a book for children, teachers and parents / N. A. Kopytov. - M.: AST-PRESS, 1998. - 240 p.
 16. Kotov, A. Ya. Evenings of Entertaining Arithmetic [Text]: for 4th grade primary school students / A. Ya. Kotov. - 2nd ed., corrected. and additional. - Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1967. - 184 p.
 17. Lipina, I. A. Development of logical thinking in mathematics lessons [Text] / I. A. Lipina // Primary school. - 1999. - No. 8. - P. 37-39.
 18. Obukhova, L. F. Age psychology [Text]: textbook / L. F. Obukhova. - M.: Yurait: MGPPU, 2010. - 460 p.
 19. Ovchinnikova, T. N. Personality and thinking of the child: diagnostics and correction [Text] / T. N. Ovchinnikova. - M.: Acad. Proekt, 2002. - 192 p.

20. Piaget, J. Speech and thinking of the child [Text] / J. Piaget; [translated from French; comment. Val. A. Lukova, Vl. A. Lukova]. – M.: PedagogikaPress, 1999. – 526 s
21. Development of the psyche of schoolchildren in the process of educational activity [Text] / edited by V. V. Davydov. - M.: Pedagogy, 1983. - 398 p.
22. Repkin, V. V. Formation of educational activity in primary school age [Text] / V. V. Repkin // Primary school. - 1999. - No. 7. - P. 19-24.
23. Rubinstein, S. L. Fundamentals of General Psychology [Text]: [textbook] / S. L. Rubinstein. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2007. - 713 p.